

Kālikā Purāṇa

By Liwen Liu, University of Toronto

Entry tags: Religious Group, Text, Purana, Hinduism

The Kālikā Purāṇa (henceforth KP) is a upapurāṇa (minor purāṇa) composed around the 10th to 12th century in Kāmarūpa, an area that includes Assam and part of Bengal today. The title Kālikā refers to goddess Kālī—addressed also as Mahāmāyā, who is a great goddess in śakti tradition. Several Manuscripts of the KP are found in Bengal and Nepal, based on which a critical edition was published by B.N. Shastri in 1991. This text is an encyclopedic work on myths, ritual practices, and iconology, providing important information and instruction on goddess worship. The KP grounds its authority in divine revelation and transmission through a lineage of sages, claiming that the purāṇa was first spoken by Brahmā, and transmitted successively through the sages Nārada, Bālakhilya, Yavakrīta, and Asita. Finally, Asita taught this purāṇa to Mārkaṇḍeya, who narrated the KP to human sages (1.16-18). The KP, according to Kooij (2021), follows a fourfold narrative structure. The outmost shell contains maṅgala verses and closing verses spoken by Brahmins. In the second shell, the sage Mārkaṇḍeya narrates the purāṇa to a group of sages (ṛṣi), addressing the myth of Satī's suicide and her reincarnation as Pārvatī. He also told a unique version of Durgā slaying the buffalo demon Mahiṣāsura, which serves as a mythological grounding of Durgā Pūjā festival. The third shell is the duties and good conduct of a king. This section is instructed by a muni named Aurva to king Sagara, demonstrating that the composition of the KP might be supported by royal patronage. The fourth shell, which is the innermost part, is Tantric teachings on general worship (sāmāya-pūjā), ritual practices during festivals including Durgā Pūjā, and pilgrimage. Detailed ritual procedures and mantras are instructed by Śiva—the narrator of this section—to his two sons. This section also includes the well-known “blood chapter” (rudhirādhyāya), which prescribes animal sacrifice and even human sacrifice. The blood chapter of the KP provides a scriptural basis for Hindu killing rituals, which are still performed even today in Bengal and Nepal. As a widely circulated scripture, the KP exerts a great influence on goddess worship in eastern India. It is considered a scriptural authority regarding rituals for worshipping Kālī and Durgā. Many ritual handbooks, such as Purohit Darpan, attribute their authority to the KP and draw ritual procedures from it. Moreover, the KP is also an important reference for later writers of dharmasāstric nibandhas. For example, Raghbandana and Viśvanātha extensively quote the KP when discussing the issue of animal sacrifice and meat consumption.

Date Range: 10 CE - 12 CE

Region: Kāmarūpa

Region tags: South Asia, India, Assam

This region corresponds to the area that scholars have hypothesized was the probable location of composition of the Kālikā Purāṇa.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Kooij, K. R. van. (2021). *Tantric Teachings of the Kālikā Purāṇa*. BRILL.
- Source 2: Hazra, R. C. (1963). *Studies in the Upapurānas (Vol. 2)*. Calcutta Sanskrit College.
- Source 3: Chakrabarti, K. (2001). *Religious process: The Purāṇas and the making of a regional tradition*. Oxford University Press.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://youtu.be/jkoByQBJFU4>
- Source 1 Description: Story-telling of the Kālikā Purāṇa in Hindi.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: https://archive.org/details/YUDC_kalika-purana-sanskrit-printed-khemraj-1908-mumukshu-bhawan-collection/mode/2up
- Source 1 Description: The Kālikā Purāṇa printed in 1908. Mumukshu Bhawan Varanasi Collection.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Inked

– with Ink

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Plant leaves

Notes: Palm-leaves

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Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Species

– Specify: Palm-leaves

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

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Specify type of paper

– Specify: According to Kooij (2021, p.3-5), the oldest manuscript of the Kālikā Purāṇa is a palm-leaf manuscript. There are also other later copies written on “country-made colorless paper.”

Notes: Kooij, K. R. van. (2021). *Tantric Teachings of the Kālikā Purāṇa*. BRILL.

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Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Notes: The palm-leaves are cooked and dried before writing. The process of making a palm-leaf-book is explained in the Devī Purāṇa (chapter 91), another Purāṇa composed in Bengal.

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Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: The field doesn't know.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Tomb

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Cemetery

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Temple

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Shrine

– Yes

Notes: The colophon mentioned that the manuscript is copied in the “city-village of Kaṅka” (kaṅkapuragrāma). Kooij (2003, p.5-6) postulates that very possibly the manuscript is preserved in the shrine of Kaṅkeśvarī. Kooij, K. R. van. (2021). *Tantric Teachings of the Kālikā Purāṇa*. BRILL.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Altar

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Devotional marker

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Cenotaph

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Church

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Mosque

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Synagogue

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Monument

– No

Specific to this answer:

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Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ **Mass Gathering Point**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

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↳ **Cave(s)**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ **Hilltops**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ **Other natural sanctuaries**

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ **Boundary markers or lines**

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ **Domestic contexts**

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

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Library/archive

– Yes

Notes: A few copies of the Kālikā Purāṇa is preserved in the Calcutta Sanskrit College Library.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Specify

– Specify: None

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

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Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: Although the field does not have a consensus on which king supports the composition of the Kālikā Purāṇa, most scholars agree that kings or political officials engaged with the composition and preservation of the Kālikā Purāṇa. Hazra (1963, p.35) proposed that the Kālikā Purāṇa is composed by Brahmins who served at the court of Kāmarūpa. Scholars beginning with K.L Barua argued that the Kālikā Purāṇa is composed under King Dharmapāla, because the name of Dharmapāla occurred

several times in the purāṇa. Kooij (2021, p.6) contended that one of the scribes could be a Brahmin appointed by the Malla king. Hazra, R. C. (1963). *Studies in the Upapurānas* (Vol. 2). Calcutta Sanskrit College. Kooij, K. R. van. (2021). *Tantric Teachings of the Kālikā Purāṇa*. BRILL.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

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↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Three scribes are mentioned in the colophon of the manuscript found in Nepal. Their names—Viśvanātha, Vyayendra, and Caturbhujā Śarma—indicate that they are possibly royal priests and ritualists who serve in the court (Kooij, 2021, pp.5-6).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some purāṇas promote oral recitation, claiming that recitation of the text is meritorious.

For example, Śiva Purāṇa (13.13, 18) claims that the recitation of purāṇas are more fruitful than sacrifices and worships. However, the Kālikā Purāṇa does not make such a claim as far as I know. On the contrary, it states that one should keep the text secret from people (90. 33).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Revealed by a high god?

– Yes

Notes: The Kālikā Purāṇa claims that the Purāṇa is revealed by the high god Brahmā. Finally, the text is transmitted to sage Mārkaṇḍeya, who narrates the purāṇa to human sages. (Kooij, 2021, p.42-44). Kooij, K. R. van. (2021). *Tantric Teachings of the Kālikā Purāṇa*. BRILL.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Revealed by other supernatural being?

– No

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Inspired by high god?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

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↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

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↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

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Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

Notes: The Kālikā Purāṇa is composed in Sanskrit, a ritual language employed in rituals beginning with Vedic sacrifices.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

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↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– No

Notes: Sanskrit is considered a divine revelation in the Hindu tradition. That is to say, Brahmins believe that Sanskrit does not originate from human, but from gods or from the eternal Vedas.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Hazra (1963, pp.86-90) demonstrated that the Sanskrit used in the Devī Purāṇa—another purāṇa composed in Eastern India—indicates strong influence by the local dialect Bengali. He summarized 19 words and expressions that reveal a debt to Bengali. It is possible that these features also appear in the Sanskrit used in the Kālikā Purāṇa. However, there is no systematic study on the language of the Kālikā Purāṇa yet. Hazra, R. C. (1963). *Studies in the Upapurānas* (Vol. 2). Calcutta Sanskrit College.

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↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– No

Specific to this answer:

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↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Divinity

– Institutions

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some religious festivals require narrating purāṇic stories in vernacular languages. However, there is no existent study on whether the Kālikā Purāṇa is recited in vernacular languages in religious events.

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Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

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↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

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Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

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Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: Although the Kālikā Purāṇa does not discuss proselytization and reformation, several scholars argued that the composition of the purāṇa is aimed at transforming the religious landscape of eastern India in the 11th century. Chakrabarty (2001) argued that the Kālikā Purāṇa is composed to popularize Brahmanism by transforming the local Tantric and tribal traditions. Hazra (1963) maintained that Maithili Brahmins composed the Kālikā Purāṇa to spread Vaiṣṇavism. The purāṇa associated the goddess worship popular in Bengal with Vaiṣṇavism, linking the local goddesses to Viṣṇu.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Many ritual handbooks circulated in eastern India attribute their authority to the Kālikā Purāṇa and draw ritual procedures from it. However, it is unclear if the purāṇa per se is employed in ritual practice.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

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Is there material significance to the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Kālikā Purāṇa states that if a written version of the Kālikā Purāṇa is placed in one's residence, no obstacle will occur to him (90. 35c-36b). However, the purāṇa does not elaborate on the material importance of the text.

Specific to this answer:

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Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Hazra (1963, pp.237-243) argued that an earlier Kālikā Purāṇa was composed around the seventh century CE. This early version, incorporating less Tantric elements, was likely composed by Smārta Brahmins. He maintained that the earlier Kālikā Purāṇa was not preserved to the present day, but was incorporated into the present Kālikā Purāṇa. However, Hazra's argument is not echoed by Shastri. Textual variation are found in the manuscripts of Kālikā Purāṇa, but they should not count as multiple versions of the same text. A critical edition of the Kālikā Purāṇa is made by Shastri (1991).

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Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

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If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Notes: The Kālikā Purāṇa is explicitly scripture.

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Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Ritual list

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Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

– Ritual manual

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

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Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Kālikā Purāṇa mentions in the first chapter that the purāṇa was first spoken by Brahmā, and transmitted successively through the sages Nārada, Bālakhilya, Yavakrīta, Asita. Finally, Asita taught this purāṇa to Mārkaṇḍeya, who narrated the purāṇas to human sages (1.16-18).

Specific to this answer:

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Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

Notes: This lineage beginning with Brahmā demonstrates the authority of the Kālikā Purāṇa.

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Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

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↳ How is the lineage established?

– Student-Teacher Relationship

Specific to this answer:

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Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Notes: Although the Kālikā Purāṇa is not a legal text, later legal treatises (dharmaśāstric nibandhas) regard the Kālikā Purāṇa as an authoritative scripture on issues such as animal sacrifice.

Specific to this answer:

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Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

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↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Lunar?

Specific to this answer:

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– Micro-temporal? (related to really small portions of time; this is uncommon).

Specific to this answer:

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– Macro-temporal? (Related to really large sections of time; kalpas in Hinduism, for example)

Notes: Chapter 24 specifies the division of time and the duration of ages (yuga).

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

Notes: The Kālikā Purāṇa specifies the time for Durgā Pūjā (Chapter 59-61).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

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↳ Planting?

– No

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

– No

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Harvest?

– No

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

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↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

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↳ Marriage?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

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↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

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↳ Divorce?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Warfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Funerary services?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Trade/commerce?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Festivals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

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↳ Frequency of festivals?

–Specify: The Kālikā Purāṇa specifies the time for Durgā Pūjā (Chapter 23-24).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s)?

–All members

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ On average, how many participants are gathered at festivals?

–number: Unspecified.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s)?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Unspecified.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Pilgramages?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ How strict are the stipulations regarding pilgrimage?

– optional (rare)

Notes: The pilgrimages prescribed by the Kālikā Purāṇa are optional practices (kāmya), which should be performed when a person wants to fulfill a particular wish.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Is encouraging pilgrimages a primary reason for the existence of the text?

– No

Notes: The description of holy places is secondary to the promotion of goddess worship, which is the primary reason for the composition of the Kālikā Purāṇa.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Are pilgrimages guided by the text associated with particular life events?

– No

Notes: The pilgrimages are associated with specific desires. Some pilgrimages are more effective in granting a boon of a son to women.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Does pilgrimage guided by this text involve/follow major routes/roads?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Is the pilgrimage conducted by walking or by other means?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Kālikā Purāṇa only commands what should be performed in the

holy places, but does not specify how one should get there.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Feasting?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

Notes: The spirit, or ātma in Sanskrit, is considered distinct from the material body. After the body perishes, the ātma takes reincarnation according to one's karma.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

Notes: Kālikā Purāṇa does not attach much importance to the discussion of ontology, because it is a practice-centered scripture.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– Yes

Notes: The mind-body non-dualism often commands the presentation of impure offerings, because the dichotomy between purity and impurity is dissolved since the material is no different from consciousness. However, although the Kālikā Purāṇa prescribes impure offerings such as blood and flesh, it does not follow the ontological non-dualism. It makes the transgressive practices (vāmācāra) secondary to the orthodox practices, claiming that impure offerings are only effective in generating supernatural powers but not liberation.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Yes

Notes: Ontological dualism is the mainstream, as Brahmanism and Śaiva-Siddhānta follow this position. Ontological non-dualism is the minority position. It is followed by Kaula Tantrism established by Abhinavagupta, who extensively explains the identity between the divine consciousness and the material world in his treatise *Tantrāloka*.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

Notes: The dead person transmigrates to one's next reincarnation, which can happen in heaven, hell, or this present world.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ In human form?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ In animal/plant form?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage, etc.)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma)?

– Yes

Notes: The reincarnation into different forms of lives in different spheres is based on the karmic retribution.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ In textual exegesis among practitioners are there debates about reincarnation?

– No

Notes: No exegesis of the Kālikā Purāṇa is found.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: There are several high gods present in the Kālikā Purāṇa, such as Śiva, Mahāmāyā, Viṣṇu, and Brahmā. However, none of them conforms to the single supreme high-god in Christianity. I prefer to describe them as a pantheon of high gods.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Kālikā Purāṇa does not specify this issue.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

Notes: Gods can grant boons when they are pleased.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: The worship of supernatural gods is considered good karma.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

Notes: Gods can be pleased by oblations. They are portrayed as emotional beings that can be happy, angry, or sorrowful.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

Notes: The Kālikā Purāṇa vividly describes the grief of Śiva when he lost his beloved wife Satī.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text does not specify whether gods can feel hungry or not, but food offerings are considered pleasing to gods.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: Gods can take reincarnations into other forms of gods.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Yes

Notes: Goddesses are organized as Śiva's wife or reincarnations of Śiva's wife in the pantheon.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

Notes: Brahmā is in charge of creation, Viṣṇu is in charge of sustainment, and Śiva and his consorts are in charge of destruction.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: Brahmā, Viṣṇu, and Śiva are the triad of high gods in the pantheon.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: Some mythical animals are present in the Kālikā Purāṇa, such as śarabha.

Notes: In addition to high gods, there are also guardian deities and semi-gods who are invoked to the ritual site to ensure the success of rituals. Bāṭukas, Yoginīs, Kṣetrapālas, and Ganapati are present in rituals, and a share of oblations must be presented to them.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text guide divination practices?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Divination by examination of the extra (animal remains)

– Yes

Notes: Chapter 67 specifies the methods to tell omens according to the severed heads of sacrificial victims.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Divination through human communication?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Divination through animal-behavior?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Divination through non-living material?

–Other [specify]: None

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Other form of divination:

– Specify: None

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Notes: It is unspecified in the text.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: The text only mentions the myth in which a high god curses another god, but it does not specify whether gods directly mete out punishment or not.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Goddesses bestow boons whenever they are pleased by offerings.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Done only by high god

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– I don't know

Notes: The text does not specify whether the reward is attained through the cause-effect principle or through the individual will of goddesses.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Done randomly

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– I don't know

Notes: The scripture does not specify what the boons are, because the boons vary according to the desires of the practitioners.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– I don't know

Notes: The scripture does not specify what the boons are, because the boons vary according to the desire of the practitioner. But very likely, the boons contain benefits that can be experienced in this life, such as a son, triumph in a battle, and supernatural powers (siddhi).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Chapter 84 of the Kālikā Purāna enjoins to follow the duties of caste and life stages (varṇāśramadharmā), and to observe the rule of purity.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

Notes: The generosity in the Kālikā Purāṇa refers to the generosity toward Brahmins and Śaiva practitioners.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Cooperation

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Humility/modesty

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Notes: Generosity and devotion are considered two important virtues by the Kālikā Purāṇa. Generosity refers to especially the generosity toward Brahmins and Śaiva practitioners. The highlight of generosity reveals the intention of the KP to promote religious donation. Devotion refers to the devotion to goddesses. The KP explains that a devotional practitioner should always think of the goddess no matter what he is doing, and should always first present food and drink to the goddess before he/she consumes them (58.5-13). In addition to these two common virtues that should be observed by everyone, the KP also specifies that a king should avoid lust, anger, greediness, rapture, arrogance, and intoxication (84.39)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Monogamy (males)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Monogamy (females)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Other sexual constraints (males)

– Yes

Notes: The Kālikā Purāṇa prescribes that one should only have sexual intercourse with one's wife at proper time, and he should meditate on Caṇḍikā for prosperity (58.8-9).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Other sexual constraints (females)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text require castration?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Notes: The text requires fasting while worshipping certain deities (55.71-72, 77.26).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Notes: The human victim sacrificed to goddesses must abstain from meat the day before the sacrifice (67.75).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– Yes

Notes: Chapter 67 requires the practitioner to wound one's own body to extract blood for offering. "Blood from the cheeks, forehead, between the eyebrows, the edge of the ears, arms, nipples, belly, under the throat, and above the navel, the region of the heart, and also from both sides one should offer to Durgā. (67.157-159)." (Translation by Kooij (2021, p.168)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– Yes

Notes: Only male adults are qualified to be sacrificed.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Notes: The text requires offering one's own blood to goddesses, but it does not command one to commit suicide as self-sacrifice. On the contrary, it prohibits Brahmins to drain blood from their own bodies, because such an act counts toward suicide (67.50).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Notes: The Kālikā Purāṇa requires one to present gold and jewels to goddesses according to one's capability (55.75-76).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: The text commands daily morning and evening worship.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Notes: The Kālikā Purāṇa does not specify particular precepts as the Buddhist scriptures do.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– Yes

Notes: Outcastes like Caṇḍālas and tribals like Mlecchas are marginalized.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– I don't know

Notes: Private worship should be performed daily.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Chapter 59-61 of the Kālikā Purāṇa prescribes rituals performed in the Durgā Pūjā, which is normally celebrated as a festival in which all the people in a community participate. However, the text does not specify whether Durgā Pūjā is a large-scale ritual or an individually performed ritual.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: Chapter 77-78 of the Kālikā Purāṇa prescribes that devotees should go to Kāmarūpa—the sacred “great seat” (mahāpīṭha)—for pilgrimage. But it does not specify any particular practices in pilgrimage sites except for taking baths in holy rivers and drinking water from the rivers. Hence, we can assume that the worship in sacred places is not distinct from general daily worship.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A chiefdom

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A chiefdom

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Notes: Although the text states that the worship of goddesses brings about welfare to the worshipper, there is no mentioning of institutionalized welfare.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: The Kālikā Purāṇa does not mention the issue of education.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: In most cases, the qualification to learn Sanskrit scriptures is restricted to male twice-born people (dvijā), that is to say, they have to be born as a man in the upper three castes.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Notes: The Kālikā Purāṇa does not discuss warfare, but it mentions that the worship of goddesses and yoginīs, and the application of kavaca (armour mantras) can generate victory on battlefields (56. 53-54,74.16).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Notes: The Kālikā Purāṇa does not discuss food production. That said, the list of food offerings for goddesses indicates local food and fruits in eastern India.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 11 CE - 12 CE

Region: Assam & Cooch Behar, West Bengal in Eastern India

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